

***Aeshna grandis* larvae detect chemical cues derived from carrion: evidence of chemically-mediated food detection? (Odonata: Aeshnidae)**

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Abstract. Odonate larvae locate live, moving prey using a range of predominantly visual and mechanical cues. However, this does not explain observations of larval Odonata in association with submerged corpses, i.e., whether larvae are attracted by chemical cues emanating from submerged dead bodies. Hence the chemosensory capabilities of larval *Aeshna grandis* previously fed on living prey were tested under circumstances in which visual and mechanical perception was impossible, using model ‘corpses’, i.e., solid, homogenised, and dialysed tilapia, in link-tank test chambers. Results indicated that *A. grandis* larvae recognised cues emanating from the ‘carrion’ responding by moving in the source direction. Larval behavioral choice tests in link-tanks were also carried out on a selection of amino acids known to be released on tissue decomposition. Larvae responded positively to taurine, proline, L-glutamic acid, and glycine by moving in the direction of the source. These amino acid triggers were assessed electrophysiologically by recording from the antennal nerve. Responses depended on both the amino acid and its concentration. A positive electrophysiological response was noted for glycine at concentrations from 10^{-4} to 10^{-8} g l⁻¹ and for taurine, proline, and L-glutamic acid at a concentration of 10^{-5} g l⁻¹. No response was recorded for glutamate over a range of concentrations from 10^{-2} to 10^{-6} g l⁻¹. Therefore *A. grandis* larvae are able to respond to non-visual cues, such as some of the chemicals released during tissue breakdown, suggesting that, in the absence of live prey, their search for food may be chemically-mediated.

Further key words. Dragonfly, Anisoptera, chemoreception, amino acids, electrophysiology, attraction

Introduction

There are a number of accounts of larval odonates being retrieved along with submerged bodies. Thus KEIPER & CASAMATTA (2001) found eight different species of odonate larvae on submerged carrion whilst HOBISCHAK & ANDERSON (2002) recovered larval *Libellula* sp. from a submerged dead pig. CLADY (1975) observed several damselfly larvae such as *Ischnura* and *Enallagma* spp. clinging to the carcasses of the Common Cisco *Coregonus artedi* (Lesueur, 1818).

In these instances there is no indication of whether the odonates were feeding directly on the corpses. However, it has been demonstrated that some species of Odonata are attracted to carrion. ROWE (1985, 1987) observed both *Xanthocnemis zealandica* (McLachlan, 1873) and *Hemianax papuensis* (Burmeister, 1839) moving towards dead prey and FULAN & ALMEIDA (2010) showed that odonate larvae actively moved towards dead tadpoles. Indeed larval Odonata have been observed feeding off dead snails and dead chironomid larvae (MILLER 1995: 15).

In terms of sensory abilities there is morphological, behavioral, and electrophysiological evidence that odonate adults can perceive chemical cues (REBORA et al. 2008, 2009; PIERSANTI et al. 2010, 2014a, b). There is also evidence to substantiate the hypothesis that larvae of some species of Odonata may have the capacity for chemoreception. The ultrastructure of the larval antennal sensilla in *Libellula depressa* Linnaeus, 1758 indicates that the sensilla may have dual roles as chemoreceptors and thermo-hygroreceptors (GIANO & REBORA 2001). Examination of the ultrastructure of the antennal sensilla of larval *Onychogomphus forcipatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) similarly revealed a structure characteristic of a typical chemoreceptor (REBORA et al. 2015).

Chemical cues emanating from submerged corpses are perceived by chemoreception in Crustacea and influence their food foraging. These cues are small molecules of low molecular weight, including amino acids, aldehydes, and sugars (CARR 1988; ZIMMER-FAUST 1989), i.e., some of the same classes of chemicals which elicited electrophysiological responses in *L. depressa* adults. The existence of chemoreceptors allowing chemically-mediated food searching as well as response to predators is therefore possible in *Aeshna grandis* (Linnaeus, 1758) since it has also been found in association with

corpses in the laboratory (Fig. 1). This possibility of chemoreception is supported by the work of PLOTNIKOVA & ISAVNINA (2006), who hypothesised that their data indicated that the antennal nerve and lateral lobe of the protocerebrum of *A. grandis* could have an olfactory function.

The aim of the current study was to assess the response of larval *A. grandis* to non-visual cues from model carrion and to investigate how any such larval response to chemical cues might be mediated by a series of four experiments. Larvae of *A. grandis* are robust and adaptable predators present in ponds, lakes, gravel pits, and ditches. This readily identified species was chosen because aeshnid larvae are traditionally considered obligate predators and are currently considered to detect prey by sight, touch or by sensing vibrations (CORBET 1999: 88 f.).

Materials and methods

Treatment of the larvae in preparation for the experiment

Thirty *Aeshna grandis* larvae were collected, with permission, from Whisby Nature Reserve and Hill Holt Woods, Lincolnshire, UK. All experiments were carried out according to the British Dragonfly Society's code of practice and were approved by the University of Lincoln's Ethics Committee.

Larvae were routinely kept in individual 1 litre glass jars containing aged tap water and Waterweed *Elodea* sp. for oxygenation. To ensure uniformity of treatment before, during, and after each experiment, larvae were placed in individual holding chambers, each containing a large number of live Brine Shrimps *Artemia salina* (Linnaeus, 1758) as a food source. The larvae were observed feeding and that they responded normally to the presence of live prey was confirmed by the reduction in the number of Brine Shrimps. Larvae were removed when feeding ceased, or after two hours if feeding continued, and returned to their original containers. They were then starved for 24 hours prior to each experiment.

General experimental protocol

To test larval responses to various chemical cues two chambers were linked together by a piece of narrow tubing 70 mm long, which had a screw thread at one end to allow it to be sealed to separate the contents of the two chambers. The design was based on that of HÖGLUND (1951) (Fig. 2). Each ex-

periment was undertaken in newly de-chlorinated, aged tap water, and the bases of the tanks were filled to a depth of 3 mm with cleaned gravel. The chambers were marked to indicate which side of the link-tanks was to contain food and which the control material. The food source was always placed in the side previously containing food. In this way contamination of the untreated chamber by a residual cue source was avoided.

All experiments were conducted in semi-darkness on a stable laboratory bench top preventing vibration. A red bulb provided a light source to al-

Figure 1. Larval *Aeshna grandis* tearing at rat pup carrion flesh although no ingestion of the flesh was noted.

Figure 2. Linked-tank choice chamber experimental apparatus used to test the effectiveness of non-visual food cues on *Aeshna grandis* larvae.

low observation of larval responses. The water temperature throughout all experiments was $18 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$. Between experiments, water and food were removed from the containers, the gravel was washed, and the link-tanks filled with fresh water and left overnight.

Each experiment using link-tank choice chambers containing the treatments described below was replicated eight times, i.e., eight treatment link-tanks were run at the same time. Alongside each treatment a further set of eight control link-tanks was run in which the food source was omitted or, in the case of the controls for the tilapia sections, replaced by a tube of similar volume. A 250 ml aliquot of the homogenised fish suspension or dialysate was added to the baited side of each chamber. The experiment was repeated and a different set of previously unused larvae was used for each experiment giving a total of 16 treatments overall.

Prior to the start of each experiment, the connecting tube between the two chambers was closed with a screw cap. A larva was added to the chamber without a treatment and allowed to acclimatize there for 15 minutes. The adjoining chamber was baited with the tilapia ('carrion') cue. The screw cap was then removed from the tube to allow any odours from the tilapia to diffuse into the chamber containing the larva and to allow free movement of the larva between the chambers. The time taken for the larva to enter the connecting tube between the link-tank chambers was recorded. Previously unpublished experiments revealed that, in the absence of a cue, larvae did not enter the second link-tank chamber at all over a 24-h period (1 440 minutes). An experimental duration time of 500 minutes allowed ample time for a larval response to occur in the presence of a food cue attractant and hence, where no response had been made within this time period, the experiment was terminated.

Experiment 1. Larval response to model carrion using choice tests

Tilapia, a readily available freshwater fish, provided a model of carrion. Three forms of tilapia were tested:

(i) Solid tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) flesh

A section of approximately 20 mm^3 of skinless flesh was cut from the whole fish and used as the model food source in one chamber of the link-tank.

(ii) Homogenised tilapia suspension

The homogenate was chosen as a cue because it had no visual characteristics that could be interpreted by the larvae as a prey item. The fish suspension was prepared by homogenising a whole tilapia, weighing approximately 420 g. The resulting homogenate was placed in a muslin bag tied with a knot and steeped in 4 l of aged tap water for 45 minutes. A 250 ml aliquot of homogenised fish suspension was added to the baited tank of the link-tank choice chambers.

(iii) Dialysate with a particle size below 10 000 Da

By filtering the homogenate through SnakeSkin™ dialysis tubing the particle size of the suspension was reduced below 10 000 Da when the homogenised suspension was dialysed through a single concentration gradient of aged tap water. The dialysis tubing had a molecular weight cut off (MWCO) of 10 000 Da. Filtration reduced the particle size of the suspension to the level of amino acids and small peptides, which were considered potential larval attractants. A 250 ml aliquot of dialysate was added to the baited tank of the link-tank choice chambers.

In each case a larva was introduced to the unbaited chamber of the link-tank.

Experiment 2. Identification of the low molecular weight molecules present in a 'press' of solid tilapia and in the tilapia dialysate

Analysis of the material arising from a 'press' of solid tilapia using GC-MS provided a profile of the amino acids most likely to emanate from the carrion on decomposition and thus be potential candidates as larval attractants. This profile was compared with the identity of the attractive particles in the homogenised tilapia dialysate, in particular, its amino acid composition.

The analysis was carried out using the EZ:faast™ amino acid analysing kit and a Shimadzu™ Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometer GC-MS-QP2010S. Norvaline™ was used as an internal standard for all tilapia preparations. In order to obtain standard deviations to confirm sample preparation consistency, all analyses were repeated three times, using separate preparations from three different fish. A six-point calibration graph was obtained for each of the free amino acids recovered, allowing accurate amino acid concentration determination in the tilapia preparations.

Experiment 3. Larval response to known small sized molecules present in the dialysate

The amino acids chosen whose size fell below the 10 000 Da MWCO were: (i) glycine, the most structurally simple amino acid in the dialysate; (ii) taurine, a known stimulatory chemical for marine organisms (ELLINGER & BOYNE 1965; MAI et al. 1980); (iii) proline; (iv) L-glutamic acid; and (v) glutamine (CASE & GWILLIAM 1961; HEINEN 1980; ZIMMER-FAUST & CASE 1982; CARR et al. 1987). The methodology used to investigate larval behavioral response to the amino acids was as described for the larval response towards the tilapia for Experiment 1.

Experiment 4. Electrophysiological investigations of the antennal response of *A. grandis* larvae to selected amino acids present in the tilapia dialysate

Aeshna grandis larvae (n = 12), with head sizes varying from 3.3 mm to 7.2 mm, were selected and their responses to a range of the amino acids recovered from the food cues were further investigated using electroantennograms (EAG).

EAG recordings were obtained using a 4-channel data acquisition controller, IDAC-4 -USB (Syntech™, Germany). The software used was Syntech EAG pro version 1.1. Micro-capillary tubes of suitable dimensions (length 100 mm, diameter of approximately of 100 µm) were prepared by heating and stretching a standard glass micropipette.

Antennae were excised under a stereomicroscope using a pair of micro-scissors. Each antenna, cut at its terminal filament, was fitted into a micropipette, and then submerged in 0.5 ml of quarter strength insect Ringer's solution to prevent drying out. A second micropipette was then fixed into the antennal base. Silver wire was inserted into the open end of each tube and the apparatus connected to the EAG controller such that the base of the antenna was positive with respect to its tip (Fig. 3). The antenna was secured to both tubes with cyanoacrylate adhesive. This procedure provided secure contact between antenna and the electrodes.

The selection of the amino acids glycine, proline, glutamine, L-glutamic acid, and taurine was based on their presence in the tilapia dialysate and/or

their previous effectiveness as chemical cues for larvae of *A. grandis* in Experiment 3. Each was dissolved in quarter strength insect Ringer's solution – the same batch of Ringer's solution was used throughout the experiments to standardise the responses. Glycine was prepared at concentrations from 10^{-9} to 10^{-4} g l⁻¹ (3.89×10^{-11} to 3.89×10^{-5} M) and glutamine was tested at concentrations from 10^{-6} to 10^{-2} g l⁻¹ (6.84×10^{-9} to 6.84×10^{-5} M). The amino acids taurine, proline, and L-glutamic acid were tested at a concentration of 10^{-5} g l⁻¹, reflecting the concentrations used by HEINEN (1980) in similar experiments on crustaceans.

Once a stable base line was achieved, an initial 5µl of 10^{-4} g l⁻¹ glycine (3.89×10^{-5} M) was pipetted into the Ringer's solution to observe cell depolarisation and confirm contact. This was represented by a vertical deflection in the oscilloscope recording trace and its subsequent return to base level.

Throughout the recordings 10^{-4} g l⁻¹ glycine was used to confirm the antennal receptors were still functional. After each test the amino acid solution was removed with a capillary tube and replaced with fresh insect Ringer's solution. A working time of 20 minutes before cell degradation and loss of electrical response per excised antenna allowed sufficient time to determine responses to the five test amino acids under consideration.

Figure 3. Diagram of the electrophysiological apparatus used to test antennal response of *Aeshna grandis* larvae to selected amino acids

Statistical analysis

The statistical package used was SPSS for Windows, Version 18. In some of the experiments using the link-tank chambers the larvae did not demonstrate a choice after 500 s, which necessitated stopping the experiment after a set time of those runs.

To quantify the experiments and take account of the censorship of the experiments where no response had been gained within the 500 minutes, a Cox's semi-parametric 'Proportional Hazards Model' was used. This test relates the time to event and at the same time allows for the effect of a covariate (in this instance variation in larval head size of the samples available for the tests). The effect of head size reflecting larval age on the rate of positive response was determined. In addition, the test allows for circumstances where the experiments are terminated because the controls show no response and enables such censored data to be analysed and provides a significance value. The assumption of the Cox's Proportional Hazard Model is that the probability of the event of interest, in this instance larval movement into the connecting tube, depends only on time. No systematic difference between the censored and uncensored experiments is considered to occur.

The graphs resulting from the Cox's Proportional Hazards Model are in the form of Kaplan-Meier survival graphs. These graphs were devised to deal with incomplete observations (KAPLAN & MEIER 1958), which can arise when censoring is required. They are used to represent and estimate the differences between 'time to events', particularly when experiments have subjects which do not complete the event within the time allotted, i.e., the experiment is censored. Interpretation of the Kaplan-Meier graphs is achieved by comparing the lengths of horizontal lines along the x-axes, which indicate the 'survival' duration for that interval (or treatment), i.e., the time the larva has remained in the chamber without the food cue. The y-axis is the cumulative proportion of subjects surviving at the time – Cum Survival. This is the proportion of larvae remaining (surviving) from the start of the experiment in the chamber into which they had been introduced until the end of the experiment. The level of probability chosen was $p < 0.05$.

Confirmation of the homogeneity of the samples for the amino acid analysis was undertaken using the Grubbs Test to determine the existence of outliers and a Repeat-Measures One-Way ANOVA. The latter was used to

Table 1. Cox's Proportional Hazards omnibus test for coefficients 'overall' significance of the response of *Aeshna grandis* larvae to three model 'carriion' (food) sources (tilapia block, tilapia homogenate and tilapia dialysate) compared to controls where no food cue was present.

-2 Log Likelihood	Overall (score)			Change from previous step			Change from previous block		
	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Chi-square	df	Sig.
391.312	86.048	5	.000	71.535	5	.000	71.535	5	.000

determine whether there were any significant differences in concentrations of amino acids recovered in the analysis of a 'press' of solid tilapia. Where no differences were confirmed the concentrations of amino acids between the replicates of the three fish were averaged.

Results

Experiment 1. Larval response to model carrion using choice tests

The effect of head size on larval choice test response was shown to be non-significant (Cox's Proportional Hazards analysis Residual $\chi^2_{(29)} = 36.050$; $p = 0.172$). The results of the comparison of response times to a section of flesh, homogenate, and dialysate of the homogenate with the controls where the cue was absent were highly significant ($p < 0.0001$) (Tab. 1). When solid tilapia flesh was used as a stimulus the average larval response time was 216 minutes (SE ± 42.9 min) with a fastest response time of 29 minutes. In the controls one larva entered the tube after 81 minutes but no others entered within the 500 minutes of experimental time (Fig. 4).

Response to homogenised tilapia as an odour cue source was more rapid than the response to the solid tilapia flesh. The first larval response occurred within 5 minutes of the start of the experiment. The mean time taken for a larva to pass into the adjoining food-containing chamber was 66 minutes (SE ± 17.38).

The dialysate of tilapia homogenate had a larval average response time of 111 minutes (± 13.92 min). The average response time to the dialysate was slower than the average response time for the homogenate fraction. However, the concentrations of amino acids were reduced by the dialysis method (Table 2).

Experiment 2. Identification of the low molecular weight molecules present in a 'press' of solid tilapia and in the tilapia dialysate

The results of the GC-MS amino acid analyses of the tilapia flesh were analysed statistically. The existence of outliers was tested using the Grubbs Test and their absence was confirmed. The Repeat Measures One-Way ANOVA confirmed that there were no significant differences between the amino acid profiles of the replicates of the three different fish ($F_{(1,2)} = 1.883, p = 0.16$) and hence the data were averaged. Twenty-seven amino acids were present at concentrations above $0.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g l}^{-1}$ in the tilapia press. Potentially these

Figure 4. Kaplan-Meier 'survival' graphs showing the link-tank choice test response of larval *Aeshna grandis* to a section of tilapia (2), tilapia homogenate (4) and homogenised tilapia dialysate (6) in comparison to the responses in the 'control' link-tank apparatus without any food cue sources (1, 3, 5). The x-axis indicates time and the y-axis the number of larvae remaining within the introduction tank, i.e., the cumulative proportion of larvae remaining from the start of the experiment in the tank into which they were introduced. The y-axis is therefore labelled to indicate cumulative survival (Cum Survival). Kaplan-Meier survival graphs were devised to deal with what are statistically considered to be incomplete observations which can arise because all of the treatment larvae have responded but none, or only some, of the control larvae. In such circumstances the experiment may be terminated or 'censored'.

Table 2. Amino acid concentrations (above $0.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g l}^{-1}$) recovered by GC-MS analysis from a dialysate of homogenised *Tilapia* using the EZ:faast™ method.

Amino acid	Concentration [g l^{-1}]
Alanine	0.00943
Glutamine	0.00613
L-Glutamic acid	0.00485
Glycine	0.00311
Leucine	0.00275
Valine	0.00028
Proline	0.00025

amino acids could all be released from decomposing tilapia and include attractants to dragonfly larvae.

However in the dialysate, which also elicited positive larval locomotory responses, only eight amino acids were recovered at concentrations above $0.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g l}^{-1}$ (Table 2), namely glycine, alanine, glutamine, glutamic acid, valine, sarcosine, proline, and leucine. The nature of the EZ:faast™ system precluded the recovery of taurine, which may have been present but unrecognised. Of those amino acids recovered by dialysis the most structurally simple amino acid, glycine, along with taurine, proline, L-glutamic acid, and glutamine were chosen for further behavioral investigation (Experiment 3) based upon their ability to attract decapod crustaceans (HEINEN 1980). A concentration of $10^{-4} \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ was utilised to reflect an abundance of the amino acids within the range of concentrations recovered from tilapia by GC-MS.

Experiment 3. Larval response to known small sized molecules present in the dialysate

Larvae ($n=16$ in all instances) showed positive responses to some of the known small sized molecules present in the dialysate. A positive response was demonstrated for glycine ($p=0.001$), proline ($p=0.001$), L-glutamic acid ($p=0.001$), and taurine ($p=0.001$) (Fig 5.). *Aeshna grandis* did not respond positively to glutamine ($p=0.212$) or the relevant controls.

The larval response time for glycine – 104 minutes (± 12.83 min) was similar to their response time for exposure to the dialysate. The larval re-

sponse to taurine – 48 minutes (± 8.74 min) – was faster than for glycine, proline – 74.3 minutes (± 18.1 min) – and L-glutamic acid – 101.2 minutes (± 29.4 min).

Experiment 4. Electrophysiological investigations of the antennal response of *Aeshna grandis* larvae to selected amino acids present in the tilapia dialysate

Electrophysiological analysis confirmed an antennal response to the selected amino acids based on applications to successful antennal preparations

Figure 5. Kaplan-Meier 'survival' graphs indicating the responses of *Aeshna grandis* larvae to the amino acids glycine, proline, L-glutamic acid and taurine. Line A – control; line B – treatment.

from 12 larvae. The responses of both left and right antennae were tested using a concentration of 10^{-4} to 10^{-8} g l⁻¹ glycine and confirmed to be the same at all concentrations. Electrophysiological analysis also revealed that there was a difference in chemoreception of the chosen amino acids.

Antennal responses to glycine were achieved at concentrations ranging from 10^{-4} to 10^{-8} g l⁻¹. Positive responses at 10^{-5} g l⁻¹ were also recorded for taurine (7.9×10^{-8} M), proline (8.68×10^{-8} M) (Fig. 6), and L-glutamic acid (6.79×10^{-8} M) which due to lack of availability of *A. grandis* specimens were only tested at that concentration. In the case of glutamine no stimulatory responses were recorded for concentrations ranging from 10^{-2} g l⁻¹ (6.84×10^{-5} M) to 10^{-6} g l⁻¹ (6.84×10^{-9} M). The applications were made to antenna from the sample of the same 12 larvae used to test glycine for which positive responses had been gained for those concentrations.

Discussion

Larval *Aeshna grandis* responded to the presence of all three forms of model carrion, tilapia section, homogenate, and dialysate by moving towards the source of the carrion models under circumstances where use of visual and mechanical cues were precluded. The experimental apparatus design and

Figure 6. Examples of cell depolarisation resulting from addition of 10^{-5} g l⁻¹ of glycine (A) and proline (B) in the electrophysiological investigation of the response of antennae of *Aeshna grandis* larvae to these amino acids. Similar depolarisation graphs represented the responses to the amino acids taurine and L-glutamic acid at the same concentrations (not presented).

the presence of gravel in the base of the apparatus together with the stability of the laboratory bench upon which the experiments were undertaken limited any possibility that vibration or visual cues were the stimuli for the positive larval responses towards the model carrion. Chemical cues emanating from the model carrion are most likely to be small diffusible molecules, since the homogenised tilapia suspension provided response times faster on average than those of solid tilapia flesh. Larval movement towards the treatment chamber (the source of the cue) through the connecting tube also suggests that the attractants are water soluble and the results indicate that larval response may be affected by attractant concentration.

Chemical analysis of the dialysate fraction confirmed that it contained small peptides and a range of amino acids including glycine, proline, and L-glutamic acid. No additional analysis was carried out to determine the total profile of the dialysate. Further analysis may reveal additional larval attractants of low molecular weight. In link-tank choice tests *A. grandis* showed positive responses to the individual amino acids glycine, proline, L-glutamic acid, and also to taurine, which could not be recovered by the analytical used but is a known attractant of Crustacea. The results of the behavioral study support the hypothesis that *A. grandis* larvae can respond to cues other than visual since they responded positively to cues from fish flesh, homogenised fish, and a fraction containing particles smaller than 10 000 kDa from the dialysate which included amino acids.

The EAG responses towards the selected amino acids recorded for *A. grandis* larval antennae supported the behavioral reactions and were positive for glycine, proline, taurine, and L-glutamic acid but not for glutamate. They also confirmed that concentration of the individual amino acids influenced the response. It was significant for glycine in particular where responses were gained for concentrations as low as 10^{-8} g l⁻¹. It is recognised that, due to the availability of specimens of *A. grandis* larvae, only a small although sufficient number of replicates was used in the electrophysiological experiments in order to determine whether or not a response was achieved using a particular amino acid and concentration. Further investigations with a greater number of larvae involved would help in confirming the range of concentrations for other amino acids that are significant and allow quantification of results. These findings for *A. grandis* are supported by similar

responses to amino acids in experiments using crustaceans for which they are also attractants. HEINEN (1980) confirmed that the individual amino acids glycine, taurine, and L-glutamic acid stimulated locomotory responses in decapod crustaceans, at concentrations as low as 10^{-10} g l⁻¹. However, he found mixtures of amino acids were more effective than individual amino acids in initiating feeding behaviours. These chemicals may therefore also account for the cited observations of larval odonates on corpses and carrion in the wild.

Aeshna grandis antennal responses to the amino acids were similar irrespective of whether it was the left or the right antenna which was examined, i.e., both showed chemosensory perception of glycine when tested. CORBET (1999: 97), when describing the predatory sequence, notes that prior to the detection of prey the antennae are not quite in line. At the point of prey detection, the antennae become parallel and converge on the prey location at which point the head orientates both vertically and horizontally. As the larvae moves towards the prey the head and antennal movements are repeated. Such behaviour is indicative of olfactory perception (KOEHL 2006) for which comparable antennal perception is needed in both left and right antenna, as demonstrated above for *A. grandis*.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) investigation of *A. grandis* antennae previously revealed that both larva and adult possess a range of sensilla and that the morphological structures present are comparable to those found in other odonate species including those morphologically considered to be chemoreceptors (COULTER et al. 2015). Along with the behavioral and electrophysiological responses demonstrated towards carrion and its decomposition chemicals, these observations support the hypothesis that *A. grandis* has a chemosensory capacity which is used to respond to the model and that the antennae are a source of the chemosensory capability used to forage for food.

There is an increasing body of observations suggesting that larvae of a number of odonate species may have a chemosensory capacity. PRITCHARD (1965) identified structures he considered to be contact chemoreceptors on the epipharynx of *Aeshna interrupta lineata* Walker, 1908. BASSEMIR & HANSEN (1980) observed four single-pore sensilla on the maxillary palp of

Agrion sp. and *Ischnura* sp. and considered them contact chemoreceptors. GAINO & REBORA (1999, 2001) identified a sensillum on the apical flagellum of the antenna of *L. depressa* larvae they considered to be chemosensory. REBORA et al. (2015) recorded a sensillum on the antenna of *O. forcipatus* larvae with an external and internal structure comparable to structures with a chemosensory function. Such cuticular structures reminiscent of chemoreceptors have also been observed in *Calopteryx haemorrhoidalis* (Vander Linden, 1825), *Ischnura elegans* (Vander Linden, 1820), and *Aeshna cyanea* (O.F. Müller, 1764) larvae (REBORA et al. 2015), and in *Epiophlebia superstes* (Selys, 1889) larvae (FAUCHEUX 2007).

Besides these chemosensory type sensilla, long filiform sensilla were observed on the antenna and legs of *A. grandis* larvae using SEM, suggesting that they could depend on more than one type of sensory cue when foraging. REBORA et al. (2004) noted similar hairs on larval *L. depressa* legs and considered them mechanosensory in function. Prior to locomotory activity during the experiments, *A. grandis* larvae were observed to exhibit leg extensions as well as antennal movements (JPC unpubl.). This action would facilitate sensory reception of the sensilla on both the antennae and the legs and in particular any mechanoreceptors present. WEISSBURG et al. (2002) pointed out that organisms, in addition to chemoreception, frequently used accessory cues such as flow or gravity, to which mechanoreceptors respond, in order to supplement information gained from chemical cues. Such may be the case in chemically-mediated food searching by *A. grandis*, although not in the laboratory experiments described in this study.

The cues used in the predatory sequence have been shown to vary dependent on the stadium and species of odonate (SHERK 1977; CORBET 1999: 88). *Calopteryx splendens* (Harris, 1780) (RICHARD 1960) and *Somatochlora alpestris* (Selys, 1840) larvae predominantly use mechanical detection to locate prey and generate a labial strike. This predisposition means that visual and olfactory recognition play little or no role in predation in such species – for example *S. alpestris* larvae which are opportunistic feeders showed an absence of response to dead culicid larvae (H. Wildermuth pers. comm.). Sensory cue responses in active feeders such as the aeshnids, which do utilize visual and mechanical cues for prey capture and feeding behaviour,

are influenced by the environment and the prey itself (CHOVANEC 1992). CHOVANEC established that when the prey was positioned in front of an *A. cyanea* (Müller, 1764) larva, prey size, and distance from the predator influenced the larval response. Therefore prey abundance in a location is an important feature which may determine the dominance of mechanical and visual cue responses in the odonate predatory sequence. A significant positive correlation between larval density and density of food organisms has been demonstrated for some species of Odonata suggesting that abundance of food is one of the determinants of larval distribution (ALZMANN et al. 1999); a response which thereby facilitates odonate optimal foraging. An abundance of Odonata larvae may also attract predators however and in this context chemoreception has been shown to be of significance including where predation is considered to depend on visual and mechanical cues.

Odonate larval behaviour is influenced by chemicals released by their predators (CRESPO 2011; PIERSANTI et al. 2014 a, b). Larvae learn to recognize kairomones in the environment derived from the predator and relate them to predator presence with a resultant alteration in larval behaviour (CORBET 1999: 148; FERRIS & RUDOLF 2007). *Enallagma* sp. reduced the frequency of their movement, feeding bites, and head bends when the damselflies were exposed to water containing chemicals arising from both pike fed on this damselfly species and water previously containing pike fed on fathead minnows, with which the damselflies were sympatric (CHIVERS et al. 1996). Such larval behaviour requires some form of chemoreception to recognise the presence of predators and modify their behaviour which provides additional support for the view that Odonata have the ability to utilise chemosensory perception. Wounded, dead, and dying organisms release amino acids, nucleotides, and organic acids into the environment (BRÖNMARK & HANSSON 2000). These chemicals are therefore most likely to be the cues to which the larvae are responding.

Aeshna grandis demonstrates both behavioral and electrophysiological responses to chemicals originating from carrion. It is this capacity to respond to chemicals from dead and damaged organisms which may initially account for the presence of *A. grandis* in association with carrion. Chemoreception

would appear to facilitate food searching at a stage before food capture, i.e., before the instigation of the labial strike when prey is in close proximity and clearly visible, which may then trigger a food capture response. It should be noted that the *A. grandis* larvae used in this study had been starved for 24 hours prior to the experiment. They were considered to be in a state of hunger when they were introduced into the link-tanks and subsequently responded positively to tilapia chemicals and amino acids emanating from the baited chamber. The experimental design would parallel a situation in which food was depleted in the area inhabited by *A. grandis* larvae.

Submerged carrion is a pulsed resource present only intermittently. As indicated above there is little evidence that carrion which is not itself dead odonate prey, is utilised as a food source despite it releasing chemicals attractive to *A. grandis*. However such carrion does attract a number of species upon which *A. grandis* larvae prey. Snails and chironomid larvae, scavengers and opportunistic omnivores feeding on detritus, as well as crustaceans such as *Gammarus* sp. which have a combined shredder/predator role, are all found in association with submerged corpses. A chemosensory capacity to locate such carrion in response to the plume of decomposition chemicals would enable *A. grandis* to access a ready supply of food, especially where the local stock is depleted and the individual larvae are starving. Under such circumstances the chemosensory ability demonstrated in this study and a plasticity of behaviour in which response to visual cues lessened in importance, would increase the fitness of the individual *A. grandis* and the species by bringing them in contact with a new source of food if they migrate in response to the attractant odour plume.

Feeding stimulants for a number of species have been identified as low molecular weight metabolites such as amino acids, organic acids, and nucleotides derived from leakage and excretion from live prey (BRÖNMARK & HANSSON 2000). Therefore it is possible that for *A. grandis* the search for live prey is also chemically-mediated by these chemicals. This view is supported by the fact that amino acids have been recovered from water in which *Chironomus* sp. and *Tubifex* sp. have been living (KREUTER et al. 2008). Both species are amongst the live prey readily consumed by *A. grandis*; Chironomidae in particular have been identified in faecal pellets derived from food

consumed by *A. grandis* larvae in the wild (GODFREY & THOMPSON 1987). That chemical mediation has a role to play in larval foraging for live prey needs to be tested for other Odonata species to confirm the validity of this conclusion.

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